

LEXICAL MEANS OF EXPRESSING SYMPATHY AND EMPATHY IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada simpatiya va empatiya tushunchalariga ta'rif berib o'tilgan va ularning nazariy tomonlari ochib berilgan. Shuningdek, bu ikki terminning farqi va o'xshash tomonlari misollar asosida yoritilgan. Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi simpatiya va empatiyani badiiy asarlarda ifoda etishning leksik xususiyatlarini aniqlash va yoritib berishdan iborat.*

Ek açıklama. *Bu makale sempati ve empati kavramlarını tanımlayarak teorik yönlerini ortaya koymaktadır. Ayrıca bu iki terim arasındaki farklar ve benzerlikler örneklerle anlatılmıştır. Bu makalenin amacı sanatsal eserlerde sempati ve empati ifade etmenin sözlüksel özelliklerini tespit etmek ve açıklamaktır.*

Abstract. *This article defines the concepts of sympathy and empathy and reveals their theoretical aspects. Also, the differences and similarities between these two terms are explained on the basis of examples. The purpose of this article is to identify and explain the lexical features of expressing sympathy and empathy in artistic works.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье определяются понятия симпатии и сопереживания и раскрываются их теоретические аспекты. Также на основе примеров поясняются различия и сходства этих двух терминов. Цель данной статьи – выявить и объяснить лексические особенности выражения симпатии и сопереживания в художественных произведениях.*

According to the Merriam dictionary the word sympathy is a feeling of sincere concern for someone who is experiencing something difficult or painful. Empathy involves actively sharing in the person's emotional experience.

When *empathy* was coined in the early 20th century, it referred to something quite different: the act of imagining one's own ideas, feelings, or attitudes as fully inhabiting something one is observing, such as a work of art or a natural occurrence. Someone experiencing empathy in this sense was actively projecting their own feelings onto someone or something else—often experiencing a bodily sensation in response to a dance, a painting, a sunset—or a wrestling match.

Empathy and sympathy are two terms that are often used interchangeably. But only one of them allows people to connect deeper than surface level. From a high level, empathy is the ability to understand and share the feelings of others, involving a deep emotional connection. Sympathy is expressing care and concern for someone's feelings without necessarily sharing those emotions yourself, focusing more on compassion and support.

Sympathy and Empathy Difference

Sympathy and empathy both involve feelings of concern for someone, but empathy goes beyond a feeling of concern to include an active sharing in the suffering person's emotional experience. To illustrate the distinction we present a sad dramatic scenario:

The oven's failure when Harry the Dog was so close to perfecting his soufflé recipe was terrible. Mabel the Cat could see that he was absolutely crestfallen, and offered her sympathy:

“Harry,” she said, “I’m so sorry about your oven, and at this particular moment.”

"I appreciate your sympathy, Mabel," he replied. "But I wish you had some empathy—though you're not a baker, so I understand it's perhaps impossible."

Mabel feels and expresses sympathy—that is, a feeling of sincere concern for Harry, who is having a difficult time. But Harry would really like Mabel to show some empathy—that is, to show that she actively shares in his emotional experience.

"Oh Harry," said Mabel, "I've seen you mixing and stirring and baking late into the night for days now and I could sense how close you were to your goal. I was cheering your progress with you. I do, in fact, empathize with you."

You'll all be relieved to know that in this fictional world an oven repair is forthcoming.

She literally wept with those who wept, while in tones of peculiar love, sincerity, and firmness, she lauded them for their noble daring, and freely expressed her entire **sympathy** with them, and likewise with all in the prison-house. — William Still, *The Underground Railroad*, 1872

As he mellowed into his plaintive history his tears dripped upon the lantern in his lap, and I cried, too, from **sympathy**. — Mark Twain, *Life on the Mississippi*, 1883

... when Mrs. Jennings considered that Marianne might probably be to her what Charlotte was to herself, her **sympathy** in her sufferings was very sincere. — Jane Austen, *Sense and Sensibility*, 1811

There was a caress in the soft winds; and the whole mood of the darkness, he thought, was one of **sympathy** for himself in his distress. — Stephen Crane, *The Red Badge of Courage*, 1895

But the letters show, as he repeats stories told to him by participants in battle, the kind of imaginative **empathy** that makes him fully deserve his reputation as a war poet. — Monroe K. Spears, *American Ambitions*, 1987

Criticism, like fiction, was an act of **empathy** for Ray, putting yourself in the other guy's shoes.

—Jay McInerney, *The New York Times Book Review*, 6 Aug. 1989

Linguistic means of describing sympathy and empathy

Verbs indicating behavior

1. tremble/tremble
2. roll/roll
3. flirt
4. caress/caress
5. admire
6. enjoy
7. rush around
8. give
9. swim
10. caress
11. extol
12. drag yourself
13. get attached/
get attached

14. jump/jump
15. praise/praise
16. chatter/rattling
17. smile
18. rush/
rush
19. look after
20. praise/praise
21. kiss

Verbs indicating intellectual activity

1. remember/remember
2. look
3. think
4. donate
5. look
6. look
7. remember
8. consider/
consider
9. watch

The group “linguistic means of describing sympathy” is the most informational and largest group in terms of lexical units. To describe sympathy, the author refers to the behavior of the characters, their internal state, mental activity, as well as the portrait of the hero. When describing sympathy, the story presents tactful manifestations such as the desire to get closer, pay special attention to a loved one, kiss, miss, etc. Verbs and adverbs play an important role. Although there are lexemes that show both positive and negative internal states of a person, which proves the awareness and ambivalence of sympathy, there are only 9 units with the meaning of negative emotion. Emotions of different intensity are also expressed using synonymous series: cheerful→ joyful→ gratifying→ enthusiastic→ happy. Most verbs refer to verbs of intellectual activity, qualitative state and interpersonal relationships. Among the adverbs, the most frequent are the adverbs “affectionately”, “sweetly” and “tenderly”, because their meanings contain the semes “happiness”, “love”. In addition, phraseological units show the state of a person in love more intensely and graphically.

Emotions are produced by the verbal code and by a verbal code. The means of emotional expression includes the phonetic means, which includes intonation, percussion, tone, alliteration, rhyme, sound production, and rhythm. V.I. Shakhovsky writes that the eyes are the most informative organ. This is proven in the story by the abundance of means of describing sympathy through the description of the kinema of the eye. The group “description of the kinema of the eye” is one of the most numerous in terms of lexical units that show the urge to pay attention to a loved one or the passion and joy of the characters are manifested through the eyes. As L. G. Babenko mentioned: the heart has a special stylistic significance when showing the emotions of characters. In the story, constructions in which the subject is the “heart” also appeared many times to describe sympathy. When it comes to describing the state of the heart, most show a person's excitement. Some scientists indicate that anxiety is a neutral emotion because a person feels excitement from both positive and negative emotions

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